

Introduction

**Developing Reading Skills for
Lifelong Learning and
Employment:**

**Evidence from
Surveys and
Strategic
Partnerships**

The iRead4Skills project addresses the critical need to enhance reading skills among low-literacy adults, focusing on Adult Learning (AL) and Vocational Educational Training (VET) programs. This brief highlights key findings from recent surveys and outlines the ongoing strategic partnerships between AL/VET centers and the iRead4Skills project. The goal is to bridge literacy gaps and foster transferable skills that are crucial for adapting to the ever-evolving job market.

Survey Results

Key Insights

Recent surveys conducted as part of the project provide essential data on reading skills, needs, and challenges. The findings focus on participants in Portugal, Spain, and French-speaking countries, with key takeaways highlighted below:

READING SKILLS SURVEY

Reading skills are most used in professional (90%) and education settings, but less in government (50%) and health, highlighting sector disparities.

- Participants predominantly read to learn new things and stay informed.
- Home-related texts (e.g., lease agreements, advertisements) are often challenging, with many participants either not reading or failing to fully understand these documents.
- Transport-related materials like timetables and disruption notices are generally understood, but specific information on strikes poses difficulties.
- Shopping: Product packaging and restaurant prices are usually understood, though complex promotional materials are less accessible.
- Health-related texts, such as prescriptions and medical leaflets, are partially understood, highlighting a gap in comprehension that can affect personal well-being.

Overall Skills and Gaps Survey

Areas Percentages

- A significant portion of participants reported that their reading difficulties negatively impacted their proficiency in other areas, such as math and technology skills.
- Personal confidence and job market readiness were also identified as areas affected by literacy challenges, with many respondents noting an improvement after receiving reading training.
- Despite the training, 40% of learners still found reading complex documents difficult, although they acknowledged improvements in related professional skills.

Reading skills strongly impact self-confidence (70%) and job market readiness (65%), influencing home life, technology, and communication areas.

Policy Implications and Strategic Recommendations

Based on the survey results, the following policy recommendations and actions are proposed to support the iRead4Skills objectives:

ENHANCE ACCESSIBILITY TO READING MATERIALS

Plain language initiatives should be actively implemented across public services and consumer industries, ensuring that essential documents (e.g., healthcare, transport) are accessible to low-literacy adults.

SUPPORT FOR AL/VET PROGRAMS

The development of authentic, context-based training materials that reflect real-world reading needs (e.g., legal documents, healthcare forms) is crucial for improving adult literacy.

Professional development programs for the AL/VET trainers should include training on using new technologies and teaching tools like the iRead4Skills system to simplify text complexity.

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Strategic Partnerships and Cooperation

■ Portuguese ■ French ■ Spanish

- 220 entities contacted in French-speaking regions, including Agence nationale de lutte contre l'illettrisme and various AL/VET centers.
- 350 entities contacted in Portugal, including the national Qualifica Centres network.
- 120 entities contacted in Spain and Argentina, with strong participation from FAEA and Fundació Gentis.

These partnerships ensure that the iRead4Skills platform is well-integrated into real-world training environments, directly impacting the target groups and improving overall literacy outcomes.

The graphic shows the language distribution of engaged entities, with French (31.9%), Spanish (17.4%), and Portuguese (50.7%) participation.

Next Steps and Future Focus

Moving forward, the project aims to:

- Continue expanding the use of the iRead4Skills system in the AL and VET center.
- Focus on scientific dissemination by presenting results at leading scientific conferences, while also investing in outreach at prominent international events, such as the World Literacy Summit 2025.
- Explore new research opportunities, such as leveraging genAI-based literacy tools to support both youth and adults in their reading journey.

CONCLUSION

The iRead4Skills project is already making strides in improving reading skills among adults with low literacy levels. By focusing on creating accessible reading materials, fostering stronger partnerships, and ensuring the dissemination of research findings, the project will continue to drive positive changes in adult learning and vocational training environments.

For more information, please contact the project coordinator, Raquel Amaro, PhD, at NOVA University Lisbon. The project is funded by Horizon Europe and will run from March 2023 to February 2026. Visit our website at iRead4Skills and follow us on social media for updates.

Contact and additional Information

Coordinator

Raquel Amaro, PhD – NOVA University Lisbon

Funding Programme

Horizon Europe

Duration

March 2023 – February 2026 (36 months)

Website

[iRead4Skills](https://iRead4Skills.com)

Social Media

